

THE IMPACT OF SOME ELEMENTS OF PUBLIC GOVERNANCE ON THE LEVEL OF FISCAL PRESSURE BY STATES TYPE

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Abstract

The structure of the fiscal system and how it prioritizes its budgetary policies and ensures the efficiency of the collection of financial resources determine in a significant proportion the degree of development of a state. The quantification of the fiscal pressure at the level of the emerging states of the European Union highlights a wide range of tax rates. It presents the degree of fiscal affordability of taxpayers compared to the average level of the European Union. The relationship between taxation and the institutional quality of the system is a topic of significant interest to researchers. The authors of this article disseminate the concept of public governance and explain the evolution of quality indicators of public governance; indicators developed and quantified by the World Bank since 1996. In the article, the authors present an econometric analysis of the concept of fiscal pressure as a dependent variable is carried out, which establishes the influence on the specific indicators of public government and not only in the period 2002-2020, for the 14 emerging states of the European Union.

Keywords: fiscal pressure, unemployment rate, global governance indicators, public governance,

1. Introduction

According to the literature, the conceptual and scientific approaches to taxation are explained as economic measures applied by adopting various budgetary policies, aiming at raising financial resources for better governance and thus limiting the adverse effects caused by a high level of taxation. The high level of taxation in emerging countries has been a topic of economic interest to economists. The phenomenon of fiscal pressure is managed as an integral part of the fiscal system and is characterized as a tool for collecting revenues through taxes and fees. For taxpayers, this phenomenon is classified as financial payment obligations.

Neumark (1937) and Pehlivan (2014) also argue that taxpayers see taxes and fees as an income for the state and an expense for them. The author Constantin Tulai is that this concept is closely related to taxation and is often used in specialized studies to characterize the level of taxation of a state (Tulai, 2003).

However, a state's taxation level cannot be assessed only according to the absolute volume of taxes, even if its evolution over time is followed. The volume of taxes and fees may change over time, provided that the state cannot change its claims on taxpayers. The fiscal policy adopted by each state is an essential tool for regulating financial and economic imbalances caused by a high level of fiscal deficit and subsequently a high level of fiscal burden, which produces adverse effects on the citizen's standard of living.

The influence of the level of fiscal pressure on public governance and the government's response to the adverse effects of fiscal pressure has been. It is a hotly debated economic topic in various studies, including the 1983 study by Wolman and All. Wolman and all (1983), Adrian Groșanu and all (2015), B. Hasan et al. (2014) and Srivastava (2009) argue that good governance by decision-makers, both nationally and internationally, has It is based on several priority principles,

such as accountability and decision-making transparency in the development of the fiscal and economic policies of the rule of law. These elements play an essential role in the economic growth of the state.

In the article presents a multiple regression with panel data, where its results will be interpreted. In the econometric analysis, the authors took as a dependent variable the level of fiscal pressure, and as independent variables, three indicators from the six specific indicators of public government (Voice and Responsibility; Government Effectiveness; Political Stability and Absence of Violence; Quality of the Regulatory Framework; Rule of Law and Control Corruption) developed following the methodology described in the study "Aggregating Governance Indicators" (Kaufmann, Kraay and Zoido-Lobaton, 1999), and two critical indicators of economic stability represented by the unemployment rate and the growth rate of gross domestic product. All these indicators will be used in the econometric analysis for the 14 emerging countries in the European Union (Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Lithuania, Latvia, Malta, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia) for the period 2002-2020. Ignoring these indicators in the various econometric analyzes of specialists in the economic field and later adopting different budgetary policies creates adverse effects on the economy and has as side effects the decrease in fiscal revenues and the increase in unemployment.

The results of this article are intended to complement the information found in the literature by presenting the significant relationship between fiscal pressure and quality indicators of public governance and providing helpful information to decision-makers to improve and streamline the economic and political environment.

2. Speciality literature.

In the literature, the optimal positive level of fiscal pressure is seen by researchers as a priority condition in the good social and economic development of public

governance in order to increase investment and social welfare.

Estimating the fiscal pressure level most frequently used in research studies is the ratio between tax revenues and gross domestic product (Liu et al 2013; Celikay, 2020; Vasileva, 2020; Paientko et al 2020).

Ungureanu M.A. (2013) argues that from the government's perspective, the level of fiscal pressure shows us what part of taxpayers' revenues will turn into tax revenue for public authorities and reports that the decrease in the fiscal pressure coefficient influences the level of the budget deficit. In connection with the present study, we identify the modern literature researchers. They empirically claim that reducing the fiscal pressure directly influences the financial stability of the state and has the potential to stimulate the economy (Alstadsaeter et al 2017; Tamai et al 2019; Celikay, 2020). Skarzauskas (2021) analyzed in a recent study the impact of fiscal pressure on the financial stability of the state in 28 states of the European Union in the period 2005-2019. It is empirical that fiscal pressure can affect financial stability by directly impacting economic growth. These researchers used the unemployment rate, gross domestic product growth, deficit and bond yields as indicators to assess economic stability. The authors show that the most decisive positive impact is identified in states with high fiscal burden and low financial stability and low fiscal burden and high financial stability. The weakest influence was identified in states with low fiscal pressure and low fiscal stability. Financial stability is still low.

Regarding the significant influences on public governance and long-term economic development, Vasiliauskaite et al (2009) state that there is still no unanimous opinion in the literature on how the tax burden affects these two concepts. Empirical evidence on this subject is divided, having different characteristics for different states, periods and explanatory variables. Existing studies do not have a clear picture of the impact of the tax burden, as it lacks a methodology for assessing all factors influencing the economy. A key component of public governance is financial and economic stability. Economists argue that national and international comparisons of fiscal pressure are possible, but its exact impact on stability remains problematic due to multiple factors of economic stability (Salaudeen et al, 2018; Celikay, 2020).

Based on existing studies, two channels of the impact of the fiscal burden on the financial stability of the state have been identified, once through the fiscal structure (Yanikkaya et al, 2018; Durusu-Ciftci et al, 2018; Valenduc, 2019; Bunn et al 2020) and the minimum level of taxation (Karagianni et al, 2012; Mao, 2017; Milasi et al 2018; Bösenberg et al 2018). Recent studies show that declining revenues by lowering the tax base negatively influences the overall image of the government (Hoene et al, 2008) and its quality. Contrary to other empirical studies, Dye et al (2008) expect governments to rely more on progressive taxation than on reducing spending to balance budgets, with the risk of increasing unemployment among citizens. The authors claim that, in addition to increasing tax rates and reducing spending, another possible response option is to

step up economic development efforts to regain the tax base that was lost by reducing the tax burden.

Jensen et al (1976) believe that local government must be in the people's best interests. So administrations need to perform well. Jones et al (2010) reaffirmed that government performance is multidimensional, so no single indicator can be used to show comprehensive government performance. For specialists, public governance focuses on how public fiscal policies are implemented and how public services are provided to citizens (Osborne, 2010).

The concept of public governance was defined by Farazmand (2004) as "a participatory process of governing the social, economic and political affairs of a state, country or local community, through structures and values that reflect society."

Worldwide Governance Indicators have been identified within the concept of public governance. These were first presented in a study launched in 1996, which aimed to initiate as many indicators as possible, which helped measure the various elements of public governance for as many states as possible and one of the most important. Often used by them for the United Nations Development Program (UNDP). The program's initiators defined governance as "the exercise of political, economic and administrative authority to manage the internal affairs of a nation. Governance targets complex mechanisms, processes, relationships and institutions through which both citizens and taxpayers exercise their rights and obligations and mediate differences (UNDP, 1997). This definition is characterized by multiple principles such as ensuring transparency, participation, accountability, the rule of law, efficiency, equity and strategic vision (Cheema, 2005).

Quality indicators of public governance can analyze the power of public administrations to develop sound fiscal policies. Bertelsmann (2017) points out that the indicators highlight the existence of significant differences within several states in terms of the executive capacity of each.

Finally, we appreciate that more and more scientific and empirical studies support the importance of the phenomenon of fiscal pressure (Eaton et al 2004; Chen et al 2017), and in this article, we analyze the evolution of economic indicators of economic stability and identify the relationship between fiscal pressure and public governance empirically, with the help of quality indicators of good governance developed by Daniel Kaufmann.

3. Case Study - Analysis of Government Influences on Fiscal Pressure in Emerging EU States

3.1. Research methodology

Panel regression is characterized as a modelling date that adapts the panel data, also called cross-sectional or longitudinal data.

The statistical representation of the regression of the panel econometric equation is as follows: $y = a_1 + a_2it + a_3x_{2it} + a_4x_{3it} + a_5x_{4it} + \dots + a_nx_{nit} + e$

In this article, we decided to use the multiple regression model with panel data as a methodology, considering the level of fiscal pressure as a dependent variable. As independent variables, we chose three indicators of public governance quality respectively:

regulatory quality, political stability, absence of violence/terrorism, and control of corruption. In addition to the three indicators supported by the WGI model, we also introduced the variables unemployment and GDP growth. The analysis was performed at the level of emerging states in the European Union. The countries included in the analysis are Romania, Greece, Bulgaria, Lithuania, Estonia, Croatia, Cyprus, Hungary, Latvia,

Malta, Slovenia, Slovakia, Poland, and the Czech Republic. The analyzed period is from 2002 to 2020. The database was taken from the World Bank and AMECO websites.

3.2. Research results.

In the first stage of the research, we present the highlighting of the descriptive statistics calculated for the existing data series. We included the maximum, minimum, average, and median calculations.

Table 1.

Descriptive statistics of data sets

	Tax burden	Unemployment	Regulatory quality	Political stability	Gdp Growth	Corruption
Average	33.02	9.24	0.02	0.00	2.97	0.00
Median	32.90	7.79	0.08	0.00	3.52	-0.04
Maximum	42.70	27.47	0.80	0.92	11.98	1.19
Minimum	25.40	2.010	-0.93	-0.90	-14.83	-0.86

Source: own processing in Excel

The fiscal pressure was 33.2%, its maximum value standing at 42.7%. The highest level of the unemployment rate (%) was 0.80%, while the minimum value was 0.02%. The median indicates that half of the values are less than 0.08% of GDP, and half exceed this level.

The average level of Regulatory quality (%) was 0.02%, the minimum value being -0.93%.

The lowest GDP growth rate in emerging countries was 14.83, reaching 11.98. The average value of the GDP growth rate was around 2.97.

Regarding the control of corruption and political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism, it is highlighted that their average value is 0.00, and the maximum is 1.19, respectively 0.92 points.

The present analysis continues by highlighting the correlation between the independent variables in table no.

Table 2.

Correlation between independent variables.

	Unemployment	Regulatory quality	Political stability	Gdp growt	Corruption
Unemployment	1.0000	-0.3216	-0.3500	-0.0056	-0.3122
Regulatory quality	-0.3216	1.0000	0.4907	0.0315	0.7334
Political stability	-0.3500	0.4907	1.0000	0.1562	0.5263
Gdp growt	-0.0056	0.0315	0.1562	1.0000	0.0501
Corruption	-0.3122	0.7334	0.5263	0.0501	1.0000

Source: own processing in Eviews 7.1

There is an inverse relationship between unemployment and indicative regulatory quality, political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism and control of corruption. At the same time, there is a direct, medium intensity relationship between the level of regulatory quality and the indicators of political stability and absence of violence/terrorism, unemployment, and GDP growth.

We also find a direct relationship of medium intensity between control of corruption and political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism, unemployment, and GDP growth. Independent variables regulatory quality and control of corruption are directly related but are not server related.

In table no. 2, we notice no strong intensity relations between the independent variables. Therefore all the above variables will be included in the multiple regression model with panel data.

Within the multiple regression model that will be realized, we took the level of general fiscal pressure as a dependent variable. As independent variables, we chose regulatory quality, political stability and absence of violence/terrorism, control of corruption, GDP growth and unemployment.

Next, we present and discuss the results of the multiple regression model with panel data.

Dependent Variable: TAX_BURDEN

Method: Panel Least Squares

Total panel (balanced) observations: 238

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
UNEMPLOYMENT	0.150728	0.047561	3.169144	0.0017
REGULATORY_QUALITY	-7.991829	0.941131	-8.491727	0.0000
POLITICAL_STABILITY	2.649718	0.697551	3.798600	0.0002
GDP_GROWTH	-0.181226	0.049828	-3.637052	0.0003
CORRUPTION	5.707064	0.721602	7.908885	0.0000
C	32.15991	0.519829	61.86636	0.0000

R-squared	0.333311
Adjusted R-squared	0.318942
F-statistic	23.19763
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000

Fig. 1 - results of the multiple regression model with panel data.

Source: own processing in Eviews 7.1

Following the generation of the multiple models, we observe that the independent variables regulatory quality, control of corruption, GDP growth, political stability and absence of violence/terrorism and unemployment are significant and have a substantial impact on the evolution of fiscal pressure in emerging EU countries. The associated probability is below the significance threshold of 1%. The value of the determination report shows that the regression model explains 33.33% of the variance in the level of fiscal pressure. If we consider the probability value of the Fisher test holds, we can say that the regression model performed is a correctly specified one, at a confidence level of about 99%.

When unemployment increases (%) by one percentage point, the level of fiscal pressure will increase by 0.150 percentage points if the other factors remain constant. When the regulatory quality increases by one

percentage point, the level of fiscal pressure will decrease by 7,991 percentage points if the other factors remain constant. As political stability and the absence of violence/terrorism increase by one percentage point, the level of fiscal pressure will increase by 2,649 percentage points if the other factors remain unchanged. When the control of corruption increases by one percentage point, the level of fiscal pressure will increase by 5,707 percentage points if the other factors remain constant. When the growth rate of gross domestic product (%) increases by one point, fiscal pressure will decrease by 0.181 percentage points if the other factors remain constant.

So, we will continue to test whether or not the disturbing factors belong to a normal distribution using the Jarque-Bera test. According to the Jarque-Bera test, the errors belong to a normal distribution under the null hypothesis, and an alternative hypothesis suggests that the errors are not part of a normal distribution.

Figure 10. Error normality testing

Source: own processing in Eviews 7.1

By testing the normality of the errors, we notice that the values estimated by skewness and kurtosis are

very close to standard values, respectively 0 and 3. These values help us conclude that the null hypothesis

of the Jarque-Bera test is accepted, so we can say that the errors in the model belong to a normal distribution.

12. Conclusions.

Global Governance Indicators can provide comparable data on the quality of public governance for a considerable number of states and an extended period. WGI indicators maintain interest in the concept of public governance and are an incentive for some states to improve the quality of governance. In the case study, we used the multiple regression model with panel data, for the period 2002-2020, with an annual frequency of data that were used. The general level of fiscal pressure represented the dependent variable. The independent variables were used regulatory quality, political stability and absence of violence/terrorism, control of corruption, GDP growth and unemployment. The results obtained indicate that all five independent variables have a substantial impact on the evolution of fiscal pressure. There is a direct relationship between fiscal pressure and the five variables. When the variables of political stability and absence of violence/terrorism, control of corruption and unemployment increase by one unit, the level of fiscal pressure increases, and with the increase by one unit of the variables regulatory quality and GDP growth, the level of fiscal pressure decreases.

However, we tend to note that WGIs are indicators that have different problems, as they are based on surveys and can be used to assess government policies. They should be used with caution as the content validity of these indicators is questionable.

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